

Creek

also known as “Mvskoke Creek”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Anj Droë, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Native American (North American) Religions, Religious Group

The Creek (preferred name “Mvskoke Creek”) is a multiethnic Native American society composed of multiple tribes, the majority of which currently reside in Oklahoma, in the United States of America. This entry focuses on ethnographic evidence that reconstructs Creek life and beliefs in 1800, prior to the reservation era, at which time the Creek lived in what is now Georgia and eastern Alabama. Beginning in 1680 and continuing through 1830, the Creek formed and maintained a powerful coalition of four main tribes, known as the Creek Confederacy. As relations with the United States grew more strained following the Revolutionary War, the Creek Confederacy was forced to cede land and move to Indian Territory in Oklahoma in the 1830s. In 1898, the tribal governments were forced to dissolve. Most members of the Mvskoke Creek remain in Oklahoma today. In 1800, when the Creek Confederacy was still in power, contact with other cultures occurred primarily through warfare, or through missionary presence in the region. However, most of the Creek still practiced the traditional indigenous religion. While a supreme high god was present, Creek religion was primarily focused on a diverse assortment of non-human supernatural beings, many of whom took the form of animals. All sentient beings, as well as some inanimate objects (including geographical features) were believed to possess a spiritual soul, and a spiritual power was believed to be ubiquitous. This power was used by religious leaders for primarily healing and other medical purposes, so much so that medicine and religion were essentially inseparable. For the Creek, religious beliefs were inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life. Therefore, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large.

Date Range: 1785 CE - 1810 CE

Region: Upper division of Alabama

Region tags: North America, United States of America

Upper division of Alabama, Alabama, USA ca. 1800

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research.
- Source 2: Murdock, George P. 1962-1971. Ethnographic Atlas. Ethnology 1-10.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nn11-000>.

– Source 1 Description: Sattler, Richard A. 2009. "Culture Summary: Creek." New Haven, Conn.: Human Relations Area Files.

– Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nn11-001>.

– Source 2 Description: Swanton, John Reed. 1928a. "Social Organization and Social Usages of the Indians of the Creek Confederacy." In Annual Report, 23–472. Washington, Dc: U.S. Govt. Print. Off.

– Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nn11-002>.

– Source 3 Description: Swanton, John Reed. 1928b. "Religious Beliefs and Medicinal Practices of the Creek Indians." In Annual Report, 473–672. Washington, D.C.: U.S. Govt. Print. Off.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: According to ethnographic evidence, the Creek were in contact with both indigenous American societies and European settler groups. See Swanton, 1928a:31, 75-77

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: "The Alabama [part of the Creek Confederacy] and Choctaw fought against each other for a long time" (Swanton, 1928a:425).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (resolved rating), "Internal warfare seems to occur once every 3 to 10 years (original code 2)" (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (resolved rating), external warfare among the Creek is rated 3.5, which is between "External warfare seems to occur at least once every two years (original code 3)" and "External warfare seems to occur every year, but usually only during a particular season (original code 4)" (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religion and society to be coterminous. Therefore, this entry considers membership to be default at birth.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Therefore, it is assumed that the religion has political support.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– I don't know

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that kings can also be high priests: "It sometimes happens . . . that the king is war-chief and high-priest, and then his power is very formidable and sometimes dangerous to the liberty of citizens, and he must be a very cunning man if the tomahawk or rifle do not cut him short" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928b:620).

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– I don't know

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that high priests can also hold political office: "It sometimes happens . . . that the king is war-chief and high-priest, and then his power is very formidable and sometimes dangerous to the liberty of citizens, and he must be a very cunning man if the tomahawk or rifle do not cut him short" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928b:620).

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that failure to attend one of the major annual ceremonies is punished: "Failure to attend the busk was penalized by the imposition of fines or confiscation of property . . ." (Swanton, 1928a:356).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "It is a standing law of the nation, 'if any person preach or hold religious [Christian] meetings, whether white or red, he shall for the first offence receive fifty lashes on his bare back, and for the second offence one hundred lashes'" (Logan, in Swanton, 1928b:320-321).

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: "It is a standing law of the nation, 'if any person preach or hold religious [Christian] meetings, whether white or red, he shall for the first offence receive fifty lashes on his bare back, and for the second offence one hundred lashes'" (Logan, in Swanton, 1928b:320-321).

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "It is a standing law of the nation, 'if any person preach or hold religious [Christian] meetings, whether white or red, he shall for the first offence receive fifty lashes on his bare back, and for the second offence one hundred lashes'" (Logan, in Swanton, 1928b:320-321).

↳ Other corporal punishment:

– Yes [specify]: Whipping

Notes: "It is a standing law of the nation, 'if any person preach or hold religious [Christian] meetings, whether white or red, he shall for the first offence receive fifty lashes on his bare back, and for the second offence one hundred lashes'" (Logan, in Swanton, 1928b:320-321).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 16000

Notes: "By 1798 there were about 16,000 Creeks and they numbered 21,792 just prior to removal in 1832" (Sattler, 2009:1).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Just as among the beings and objects in nature there were certain which possessed or acquired exceptional supernatural powers, so there were certain men who were possessed of such power or were mediums for its expression. They were also versed in the powers possessed by other created things and hence were partly prophets or soothsayers and partly doctors, while some of them occupied official or semiofficial positions and became priests" (Swanton, 1928b:614).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: "At the head of the priesthood [in] each town was the hilis-haya or 'medicine maker,' who communicated the necessary spiritual qualities to the medicines at the annual busk, had general charge of the public health, protected all from ghosts, and so on" (Swanton, 1928b:620).

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "Just as among the beings and objects in nature there were certain which possessed or acquired exceptional supernatural powers, so there were certain men who were possessed of such power or were mediums for its expression" (Swanton, 1928b:614).

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that isti poskalgi ("fasting men", a term which applies to most doctors and religious leaders) must first receive training in the local medicinal practices, then complete a long fast and initiation ceremony before acquiring the powers and abilities associated with this particular religious office. See Swanton, 1928b:617-621 for more information.

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that powers differ depending on whether they are associated with kīlas ("knowers" or prophets), alektca (priests or doctors), or hillis-haya (medicine makers). See Swanton, 1928b:615-621 for more information.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that if religious medical practitioners give the wrong advice, they are considered to be at fault and are subsequently punished: "Because a child was suddenly taken ill, and died, on the physician's [religious leader's] false evidence, the father went to the poor helpless old woman who was sitting innocent, and unsuspecting, and sunk his tomahawk into her head, without the least fear of being called to an account" (Swanton, 1928b:633).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: "These references show that at that time each town of any importance had a kind of public square [also referred to as ceremonial grounds] and often a mound near by surmounted by public buildings or the residence of the chief" (Swanton, 1928a:174). See Swanton, 1928a:174-190 for more information on the ceremonial grounds and associated structures.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: "The square is the place for all public meetings, and the performance of all their principal warlike and religious ceremonies" (Bartram, in Swanton, 1928a:182).

Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: "The square is the place for all public meetings, and the performance of all their principal warlike and religious ceremonies" (Bartram, in Swanton, 1928a:182).

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– I don't know

Notes: While ethnographic evidence indicates that religious significance is ascribed to specific sites, it is unclear whether these sites are considered sacred: "According to the idea of the southern Indians, something of the supernatural attached to every created thing, every animal, plant, stone, stick, body of water, geographical feature, and even to objects which man himself had made" (Swanton, 1928b:489).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "Bartram adds that according to native belief not merely man but every living creature had a spirit or soul that could exist apart from the body and that some had reported that 'a pattern or spiritual likeness of everything living, as well as inanimate, exists in another world'" (Bartram, in Swanton, 1928b:515).

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: "Bartram adds that according to native belief not merely man but every living creature had a spirit or soul that could exist apart from the body and that some had reported that 'a pattern or spiritual likeness of everything living, as well as inanimate, exists in another world'" (Bartram, in Swanton, 1928b:515).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "This world above was thought to be the realm of departed souls as well as the dwelling place of many supernatural beings" (Swanton, 1928b:480).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "This world above was thought to be the realm of departed souls as well as the dwelling place of many supernatural beings" (Swanton, 1928b:480).

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: "This world above was thought to be the realm of departed souls as well as the dwelling place of many supernatural beings" (Swanton, 1928b:480).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: "This world above was thought to be the realm of departed souls as well as the dwelling place of many supernatural beings" (Swanton, 1928b:480).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Notes: "According to Adair . . . the bad spirits in the west accompany and have power over the vicious . . . the bad spirits were the ghosts of the dead, or at any rate spirits associated with the western world through which the soul first passed" (Swanton, 1928b:510-511).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "In the accounts of burial customs, as well as in those of marriages, there are considerable differences, and here again it is evident that the customs themselves were diverse" (Swanton, 1928a:388).

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "When any of them die at a distance, if the company be not driven and pursued by the enemy, they place the corpse on a scaffold, covered with notched logs to secure it from being torn by wild beasts, or fowl of prey; when they imagine the flesh is consumed, and the bones are thoroughly dried, they return to the place, bring them home, and inter them in a very solemn manner" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928b:389).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: "The dead are buried in a sitting posture . . ." (Adair, in Swanton, 1928b:392).

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

Notes: "When any of them die at a distance, if the company be not driven and pursued by the enemy, they place the corpse on a scaffold, covered with notched logs to secure it from being torn by wild beasts, or fowl of prey; when they imagine the flesh is consumed, and the bones are thoroughly dried, they return to the place, bring them home, and inter them in a very solemn manner" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928b:389).

↳ Feeding to animals:

– Yes

Notes: "When any of them die at a distance, if the company be not driven and pursued by the enemy, they place the corpse on a scaffold, covered with notched logs to secure it from being torn by wild beasts, or fowl of prey; when they imagine the flesh is consumed, and the bones are thoroughly dried, they return to the place, bring them home, and inter them in a very solemn manner" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928b:389).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: "Formerly horses were killed at the grave in order that their spirits might carry the soul toward the spirit land" (Speck, in Swanton, 1928a:394).

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: "Formerly horses were killed at the grave in order that their spirits might carry the soul toward the spirit land" (Speck, in Swanton, 1928a:394).

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "The dead are buried in a sitting posture, and they are furnished with a musket, powder and ball, a hatchet, pipe, some tobacco, a club, a bow and arrows, a looking glass, some vermilion and other trinkets, in order to come well provided in the world of spirits" (Romans, cited in Swanton, 1928a:392).

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: ". . . he was drest in his finest apparel, having his gun and pouch, and trusty hiccory bow, with a young panther's skin, full of arrows, along side of him, and every other useful thing he had been possessed of . . ." (Adair, in Swanton, 1928a:390).

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: "The modern Indians bury all their movable riches, according to the custom of the

ancient Peruvians and Mexicans, insomuch, that the grave is heir of all" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928a:391).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "Jackson Lewis [an informant] told me that in Alabama, where he was born, burial inside the house was usual. The grave was dug in one corner flush with the wall, for there were then no floors, and after the body had been placed within, they raised a little house over it, 2 ½ or 3 feet high, and covered it with split plank, laid close together. They daubed the sides and top with a thick coating of clay and used the grave as a bed" (Swanton, 1928a:395).

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: "Jackson Lewis [an informant] told me that in Alabama, where he was born, burial inside the house was usual. The grave was dug in one corner flush with the wall, for there were then no floors, and after the body had been placed within, they raised a little house over it, 2 ½ or 3 feet high, and covered it with split plank, laid close together. They daubed the sides and top with a thick coating of clay and used the grave as a bed" (Swanton, 1928a:395).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "This world above was thought to be the realm of departed souls as well as the dwelling place of many supernatural beings" (Swanton, 1928b:480).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, High Gods, a supreme high god is "Present but not active in human affairs" (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: "All of the facts brought out must mean that an actual connection was supposed to exist between the sun and the busk fire and thus between the celestial deity behind the sun and this fire, and, as Adair himself points out elsewhere, that the renewal of the fire was an actual renewed presence of the deity among them, the old fire having become polluted by long separation from its source." (Swanton, 1928b:484-485).

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that supernatural beings other than the high god are worshipped: "Some mythic supernatural beings have already been mentioned, but there were a number of others, many of which caused sickness" (Swanton, 1928b:496). See Swanton, 1928b:485-498 for more information.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Both traditionalist and Christian Creeks maintain low grave houses over the graves for the use of the returning souls. Some classes of the dead, such as women who died in childbirth or unavenged murder victims, were considered unable to complete the journey and to wander lost or become malevolent ghosts at the site of their death" (Sattler, 2009:13).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Thus there is a Texas-Alabama story about a man who went out to hunt raccoons and on the way was joined by a ghost under the guise of a person well known to him" (Swanton, 1928b:511).

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The ghost of the dead man was supposed to be the efficient cause of [disease]" (Swanton, 1928b:651).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Some mythic supernatural beings have already been mentioned, but there were a number of others, many of which caused sickness" (Swanton, 1928b:496). See Swanton, 1928b:485-498 for more information.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that some supernatural beings are visible: "The 'tie snake' [mythological water spirit] is an inch and a half in diameter and short, but it is very strong. It is white under the throat, but black over the rest of the body, and its head is crooked over like the beak of a hawk" (Swanton, 1928b:492). See Swanton, 1928b:492-494 for more information on visible supernatural beings.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "Among the Texas Alabama the hoot owl (o'pa) informed prophets when a death or some other misfortune was about to take place" (Swanton, 1928b:496).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: "Among the Texas Alabama the hoot owl (o'pa) informed prophets when a death or some other misfortune was about to take place" (Swanton, 1928b:496).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "They [fairies] were strong and handsome, with fine figures, and sometimes they allowed themselves to be seen by a human being, who then talked about them continually and followed wherever they led, into forests, swamps, etc. Sometimes the victim died in these desolate spots, but at others he came to his senses and got back home. The mental disease which they thus induced seems to have been a kind of temporary insanity" (Swanton, 1928:496-497).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: ". . . the great chieftain of the thunder, is very cross, or angry when it thunders . . ." (informant in Adair, in Swanton, 1928b:486).

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Multiple, e.g., zoomorphism, extreme strength, and enlarged physical features

Notes: For more information on these and other attributes of non-human supernatural beings, see Swanton, 1928b:489-498.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "Aboriginal religion is polytheistic, with several gods who reside above, and a multitude of spirits, who primarily reside under the earth. They also believe in a pervasive spiritual power (hiliswa) that permeates the universe and inheres to varying degrees in persons, places, and objects" (Sattler, 2009:11).

Supernatural Monitoring

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that supernatural punishment is present: "Much behavior was regulated by gossip or by fear of divine retribution for violations of sacred law" (Sattler, 2009:11). However, supernatural punishment is not described in detail.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "Much behavior was regulated by gossip or by fear of divine retribution for violations of sacred law" (Sattler, 2009:11)

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of messianic beliefs.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– I don't know

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the only situation in which celibacy is required is for widowed women, following the death of their husband, over a period of four years: "The [Creek] widows are obliged to live a chaste single life, for the tedious space of four years" (Adair, cited in Swanton, 1928a:392).

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: "The [Creek men] will not cohabit with women while they are out at war; they religiously abstain from every kind of intercourse even with their own wives, for the space of three days and nights before they go to war, and so after they return home, because they are to sanctify themselves" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928a:412).

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: "Adultery was punished among the Creeks and other southern tribes in such a striking manner that almost every traveler in that section has recorded something about the custom" (Swanton, 1928a:346).

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: "Adultery was punished among the Creeks and other southern tribes in such a striking manner that almost every traveler in that section has recorded something about the custom" (Swanton, 1928a:346).

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: "The [Creek men] will not cohabit with women while they are out at war; they religiously abstain from every kind of intercourse even with their own wives, for the space of three days and nights before they go to war, and so after they return home, because they are to sanctify themselves" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928a:412).

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: "Ceremonies or fasts of a somewhat extemporaneous character were undertaken from time to time in cases of national distress" (Swanton, 1928b:534).

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: "This is the reason that several of their old men recommend, and say, that formerly their greatest chieftains observed a constant rule in their diet, and seldom ate of any animal of a gross quality, or heavy motion of body, fancying it conveyed a dulness through the whole system, and disabled them from exerting themselves with proper vigor in their martial, civil, and religious duties" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928b:517). See Swanton, 1928b:517-521 for more information on food taboos.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required body alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: "[Prisoners] are generally sacrificed before their conquerors set off for war with their ark and supposed holy things" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928a:423).

↳ Foreign, slaves:

– Yes

Notes: "[Prisoners] are generally sacrificed before their conquerors set off for war with their ark

and supposed holy things" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928a:423).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of sacrifice of children.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of self-sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: "They sacrifice in the woods, the milt, or a large fat piece of the first buck they kill, both in their summer and winter hunt; and frequently the whole carcass" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928b:516).

Destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: "The Creeks regularly make a Burnt Offering of what they conceive to be the most delicious Parts of every Animal taken in Hunting, before they presume to taste a Mouthful" (Pope, in Swanton, 1928b:517).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: "... the Indian women always throw a small piece of the fattest of the meat into the fire when they are eating, and frequently before they begin to eat. Sometimes they view it with a pleasing attention, and pretend to draw omens from it. They firmly believe such a method to be a great means of producing temporal good things, and of averting those that are evil. . . the Indian men observe the daily sacrifice both at home, and in the woods, with new-killed venison; but . . . otherwise they decline it" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928b:517).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of multiple large-scale ceremonies and rituals, including an annual ceremony performed at the beginning of the year (Swanton, 1928b:546-614), a ritual for adult males involving brewing and drinking a special type of tea referred to as black drink (Swanton, 1928b:538-544), and many dances and feasts held on or near the ceremonial grounds (Swanton, 1928b:521-538).

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: "It [black drink] is a gentle diuretic, and, if taken in large quantities, sometimes affects the nerves" (Schoolcraft, in Swanton, 1928b:538).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of multiple extra-ritual in-group markers, including long hair styled in braids and face painting. See questions below for details.

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: "This is the reason that several of their old men recommend, and say, that formerly their greatest chieftains observed a constant rule in their diet, and seldom ate of any animal of a gross quality, or heavy motion of body, fancying it conveyed a dulness through the whole system, and disabled them from exerting themselves with proper vigor in their martial, civil, and religious duties" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928b:517). See Swanton, 1928b:517-521 for more information on food taboos.

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: "While the hair was always made into four braids the beaded ornaments at the ends were for festivals or when the owner was going to town" (Swanton, 1928b:524).

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Paint

Notes: "Facial painting was employed to indicate rank in the town. Persons bearing the title of miko or hiniha wore black paint on one side of the face and red on the other, coloring either the whole face or only the space around the eyes. The second pattern belonged to ordinary initiated men having the title taskaya and consisted of four stripes, from the cheek-bone to the angle of the jaw, alternating in red and yellow" (Speck, in Swanton, 1928a:305).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community, the Creek had three levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a

chiefdom (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 33).

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: "A portion of the harvest, however, each family contributed to a large corncrib, which Bartram says was called 'the king's crib.' This constituted a reserve supply upon which to fall back when the private granaries gave out" (Swanton, 1928a:444).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Notes: While ethnographic evidence indicates that care for the elderly is present, it is not clear the extent to which it is institutionalized: "Sometimes an old man whose children were grown up, or who for any reason was alone in the world, would travel about from one to another of the houses of his female kin. He would say, 'Well, I am going to my home,' and make for the house of someone who had never seen him before. In later times this struck the young people as very presumptuous, but it was the old law" (Swanton, 1928a:170).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that isti poskalgi ("fasting men", a term which applies to most doctors and religious leaders) must first receive formal training in the local medicinal practices. See Swanton, 1928b:617-621 for more information.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that isti poskalgi ("fasting men", a term which applies to most doctors and religious leaders) must first receive formal training in the local medicinal practices. See Swanton, 1928b:617-621 for more information.

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: "Both men and women could be doctors" (Swanton, 1928b:614).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in communal facilities (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: "The T'ast'an' agis were also the native police, the Big Warrior being 'chief of police'; they carried out the decisions of the miko and the isti' atcag' agis, and they punished any one who failed to obey the laws and regulations of the council or who failed to attend the annual busk" (Swanton, 1928a:297).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic indicates that chiefs serve as judges: "Decisions [on criminal cases] made by the chiefs in council are carried into effect implicitly" (Schoolcraft, in Swanton, 1928a:320). See Swanton, 1928a:320 for more information.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "The T'ast'an' agis were also the native police, the Big Warrior being 'chief of police'; they carried out the decisions of the miko and the isti' atcag' agis, and they punished any one who failed to obey the laws and regulations of the council or who failed to attend the annual busk" (Swanton, 1928a:297).

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: "In cases of capital punishment, the executioner is selected from a body of men called 'the Light Horse'" (Schoolcraft, in Swanton, 1928a:320).

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: "After all these inflictions, the judge banishes her from the country and places her in the hands of her parents, with orders, upon pain of exemplary punishment, not to permit her to enter into any place of the province. The parents receive her, and as soon as they cover her with a mantle they lead her away into a place where she is never seen by any Indian of the country . . ." (Garcilasso in Shipp, in Swanton, 1928a:346).

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: "The adulterer's ears are flashed off close to his head, for the first act of adultery, because

he is the chief in fault. If the criminals repeat the crime with any other married persons, their noses and upper lips are cut off" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928a:350).

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: "For the first breach of the marriage faith they crop her ears and hair, if the husband is spiteful: either of those badges proclaims her to be a whore . . . for the hair of their head is their ornament . . . As the offender cuts a comical figure among the rest of the women, by being trimmed so sharp, she always keeps her dark winter hot house, till by keeping the hair moistened with grease, it grows so long as to bear tying" (Adair, in Swanton, 1928a:350).

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: "Failure to attend the busk was penalized by the imposition of fines or confiscation of property . . ." (Swanton, 1928a:356).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Because the Creek possess a police force and institutionalized judges and enforce punishment, it is assumed that they have a formal legal code.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: "In Tukabahchee and all of those towns of which the ancient organization has been preserved, either in the memories of the Indians or in fact, there were three general classes of war officials" (Swanton, 1928a:297).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 149, Scale 1 [of Cultural Complexity] - Writing and Records, the Creek possess only non-written records (Murdock and Provost, 1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the Creek have named months, divided into two groups

based on whether they fall into the category of winter or summer. See Swanton, 1928a:400 for more information.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society itself, this entry assumes that the religious group provides food for itself. The Creek depend primarily on small-scale agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation), with gathering (SCCS Variable 203, Dependence on Gathering), hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting), and fishing (SCCS Variable 205, Dependence on Fishing) as a secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas columns 7 and 28).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Creek depend primarily on small-scale agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation), with gathering (SCCS Variable 203, Dependence on Gathering), hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting), and fishing (SCCS Variable 205, Dependence on Fishing) as a secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas columns 7 and 28).